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ROLE OF HOMOEOPATHIC PRESCRIBING METHODOLOGY IN THE TREATMENT OF UROLITHIASIS: A CASE REPORT

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Urolithiasis is a frequently encountered clinical problem affecting both the sexes of various age groups and even children. Its prevalence is increasing globally. The treatment for kidney stones usually depends on their size, site and composition. This case report explores the potential of homoeopathy in the treatment of urinary calculus. Case profile: A patient of urolithiasis reported in a clinical setting. Detailed case taking of the patient was done and individualized homoeopathic medicine was prescribed on the basis of totality of symptoms after repertorization along with an organopathic medicine. *Calcarea carbonica* was prescribed as the individualized medicine followed by *Berberis vulgaris* ϕ as an organ specific medicine. The clinical status of the patient was analyzed by ultrasonography imaging. Results: Mixed approach of constitutional and organopathic treatment yielded encouraging results. There was symptomatic relief of the patient and post-treatment ultrasonography showed no calculus after homoeopathic interventions. Individualized medicine, *Calcarea carbonica* in different potencies followed by *Berberis vulgaris* ϕ was found effective in speedy removal of the calculus. Conclusion: *Calcarea carbonica*, prescribed in this case, has limited documentation in the homoeopathic literature regarding its clinical utility in urolithiasis, yet, this constitutional medicine acted favourably in alleviating the morbidity. The organopathic medicine, *Berberis vulgaris* has definitive action on urinary system. The synergistic effect of individualized medicine with organ specific medicine has paved a novel approach in the treatment of urolithiasis.

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INTRODUCTION

Statistically 5–15% of the population is affected by urolithiasis worldwide. ^[1] The incidence of renal stones shows wide regional variation with respect to their location. In India, stones in the upper and lower urinary tract are most common. ^[2] Super saturation of urine is supposed to be the fundamental cause for composition of any type of stone. Kidney stones of various compositions such as calcium oxalate stones, cystine stones, struvite stones and uric acid stones may cause morbidity to a great extent. Calcium stones are the most common in adults and children. ^[3] Most cases of renal stones are idiopathic and present with loin or abdominal pain, and macro- or microscopic haematuria. The renal colic is primarily caused by dilation, stretching, and spasm because of acute ureteral obstruction. Stones of size less than 5 mm, i.e. less than the diameter of ureter, usually pass spontaneously. ^[4] As per conventional system, stones of size between 5 to 7 mm have 50% chance of removal whereas those above 7 mm surpasses the diameter of the ureter and thus are unable to pass out. The stones of size greater than 7 mm diameter almost always require surgical intervention. ^[5] Lowering the super saturation of urine using diet and medication is supposed to be the only therapy to prevent stone formation. Homoeopathy is emerging as the preferred mode of treatment among the patients of urolithiasis. ^[6] Effective homoeopathic treatment decreases recurrence of stone formation and need for surgical procedures for stone removal. ^[3]

Constitutional homoeopathic prescribing, also called as classical homoeopathy, is based on patient's physical, mental and emotional aspect, stated by *Samuel Hahnemann* as holistic approach in the treatment of any disease whereas organopathic prescriptions are based on the *Paracelsus* principle. In organopathic approach, the given drugs affect given organs/ parts by self-selective preference. Doctors like *JH Clarke*, *RT Cooper*, *CM Boger* and *JC Burnett* have stated their experiences on the importance and usefulness of organopathic remedies especially in scarcity of guiding symptoms, causations and miasmatic background in a case. ^[7] The organopathic treatment approach is older than classical homoeopathic prescribing. ^[8]

This case report investigates both constitutional and organopathic approach that is different from the classical concept, nonetheless homoeopathic in its foundation. ^[9] Organopathic approach describes a treatment practice where case-taking focuses on locality and remedy selection on the symptoms of organs or organ-systems. This approach implies that the vital force creates disease in the organs and those organs and organ-systems are interactive parts of the whole. ^[10]

A large number of homoeopathic literature for treatment of urolithiasis is available. The present case report is another effort in this regard. The objective of this case report is to explore the effectiveness of organopathic medicine, i.e. *Berberis vulgaris* ϕ as an adjunct to the homoeopathic constitutional medicine, i.e. *Calcarea carbonica* for speedy removal of the renal calculus.

CASE SUMMARY

A 28-year-old male patient reported at Gaurang Clinic and Centre for Homoeopathic Research on 31st May 2012 with recurrent mild pain in lower abdomen radiating to left lumbar region with intermittent burning urination since one week.

Mental picture

The patient was timid, confused, irresolute and pessimistic with want of self-confidence. He had dreams of fright or of unsuccessful efforts to do various things. He was dull and indolent with aversion to work. He got offended easily and was of brooding nature.

Physical generals

He had tendency to take cold easily and in general, cold aggravated. He had sweating on his palms and soles.

Investigations

On USG dated 28.05.2012, a calculus in left upper ureter measuring approximately 9mm with minimal back pressure changes was seen. The report was brought by the patient during the first visit (31.05.2012) [Figure 1(A) (i & ii)].

Figure 1(A) (i) Ultrasound image before treatment.

Figure 1(A) (ii) Ultrasound report before treatment.

Repertorization and Repertorial analysis

Repertorization was done by using Synthesis repertory taking into account the following symptoms:

Timidity of mind, confusion, irresolution, indecisiveness, pessimism, want of self-confidence, dullness, sluggishness, difficulty in thinking, poor comprehension, indolence with aversion to work, easily offended, brooding nature; dreams of unsuccessful efforts to do various things, dreams of fights; tendency to take cold, aggravation from cold and profuse perspiration on palms and soles.

After repertorization, *Silicea* scored maximum 31 marks covering 12 symptoms; *Calcarea carb.* scored 30 marks covering maximum 14 symptoms; *Natrum mur.* scored 28 marks covering 13 symptoms; *Nux vomica* scored 28 marks covering 12 symptoms; *Sepia* scored 27 marks covering 11 symptoms followed by *Lycopodium*, *Sulphur*, *Baryta carb.*, *Phosphorus*, *Pulsatilla*, *Nitric acid*, *Kali carb.*, *Mercurius*, *Petroleum* and *Graphites* [Figure 2].

Repertorisation Table

Patient Name : ██████████ 0 Reg.No. : 6113 Rep_Date : 31/05/2012

Normal Repertorisation

	Sil	Calc	Nat-m	Nux-v	Sep	Lyc	Sulph	Bar-c	Phos	Puls	Nit-ac	Kali-c	Merc	Petr	Graph
Totally Symptoms Covered	31	30	28	28	27	26	26	25	24	24	23	23	22	22	21
[C] [Mind]Timidity.	4	3	2	2	3	3	3	3	3	4	2	3	2	3	2
[C] [Mind]Dreams:Unsuccessful efforts to:Do various things		1													
[C] [Mind]Dreams:Fights.	1		2			1			1	1		1			
[C] [Mind]Confusion of mind:	3	3	3	3	3	2	2	2	3	2	1	2	3	3	2
[C] [Mind]Irresolution, indecision:	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	4	2	2	1	1	2	3	2
[C] [Mind]Pessimist:			1	1	2	1		1			1				1
[C] [Mind]Confidence:Want of self:	3	1	2	1		2	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	1
[C] [Mind]Dullness, sluggishness, difficulty of thinking and comprehend	3	3	3	2	3	3	3	3	3	3	2	3	2	2	3
[C] [Mind]Indolence:Aversion to work:	1	2	3	3	3	2	3	1	3	2	3	2	2	1	3
[C] [Mind]Offended easily:	2	3	2	3	2	3	2		1	2	1		1	2	2
[C] [Mind]Brooding:		1		1	1	1	1	1			1				
[C] [Generalities]Cold:Tendency to take, taking cold agg	3	3	3	3	3	3	2	3	2	2	3	3	3	2	2
[C] [Generalities]Cold Agg.	3	3	2	3	3	3	3	3	2	3	3	3	2	2	3
[C] [Extremities]Perspiration:Hand:Palm:	3	2	1	3	3	1	3	1	2		1	2	2	1	
[C] [Extremities]Perspiration:Foot:Sole:	3	2	2				2	1		2	3	1	2	1	

Symptoms 1 to 15 Total Symptoms : 15 Remedies 1 to 15 Total Remedies : 615

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Figure 2. Repertorization Chart

Remedy selection/ First prescription (31st May 2012)

On the basis of repertorial analysis and in consultation with Materia Medica, first prescription was made on 31.05.2012, as stated below:

1. *Calcarea carb.* 30/ one dose (to be taken early morning on empty stomach),
2. *Berberis vulgaris φ*, ten drops thrice daily for 30 days (from the second day onwards).

RESULTS

After the first prescription, i.e. *Calcarea carbonica* 30, one dose followed by ten drops of *Berberis vulgaris φ*, thrice daily for 30 days, the patient reported improvement in respect of pain in lower abdomen and left lumbar region with remarkable relief in burning micturition [Table 1]. However, since the patient did not get complete relief, the constitutional medicine was repeated, i.e. *Calcarea carbonica* 30, one dose followed by ten drops of *Berberis vulgaris φ*, thrice daily for 30 days [Table 1]. During the 3rd visit, the patient had complete recovery symptomatically and clinically, supported by normal USG imaging and report [[Figure 1(B) (i & ii)]. But to prevent recurrence, the constitutional remedy, i.e. *Calcarea carbonica* in 200 potency, one dose, was prescribed followed by ten drops of *Berberis vulgaris φ*, thrice daily for another 30 days. Thereafter, in the subsequent visit, no medicine was prescribed as per the principles of Homoeopathy.

Table 1 Follow-up of the case.

Date	Remedy response/ Investigations	Medicines/ Potencies	Dosage/ Repetition	Remarks
29.06.2012	Relief of pain in lower abdomen and left lumbar region; burning micturition was reduced.	1. <i>Calcarea carb.</i> 30; 2. <i>Berberis vulgaris</i> ϕ	1. Single dose 2. 10 drops thrice daily for 30 days	Medicines were repeated to achieve permanent cure.
27.08.2012	No pain in the flanks and no burning pain during micturition.	1. <i>Calcarea carb.</i> 200; 2. <i>Berberis vulgaris</i> ϕ	1. Single dose 2. 10 drops thrice daily for 30 days	The constitutional medicine was repeated in higher potency (200) along with organ remedy, to prevent recurrence. The patient was advised to submit the ultrasonography report during the next visit.
28.09.2012	No complaint. USG dated 27.09.2012 showed normal study with no evidence of calculi [Figure 1(B) (i) & (ii)].	No medicine	-	The patient was cured.

Figure 1(B) (i) Ultrasound image after treatment.

Figure 1(B) (ii) Ultrasound report after treatment.

DISCUSSION

The above case report shows that homoeopathic medicines are effective in the treatment of urolithiasis. In this case, *Calcarea carb.* in 30 and 200 potencies was prescribed which covered the totality of symptoms of the patient and it has shown positive results with cure of the patient whereas *Berberis vulgaris φ* was selected following organopathic approach which facilitated to alleviate the symptoms more quickly. *Berberis vulgaris φ* is known to be indicated in left sided renal colic with stitching, cutting and burning pain from left kidney following course of left ureter into bladder and urethra.^[11]

The general concept in Homoeopathy towards treatment of the sick is 'Treat the patient not the disease.'^[7] The followers of Homoeopathy today, widely vary in their approaches for case-taking, analysis and prescribing. Different approaches have been developed which differ from Hahnemann's classical approach.^[10] The present study is in support of the earlier studies that showed the effectiveness of homoeopathic interventions in urological disorders^[12,13,14,15,16,17,18,19,20,21,22] particularly in urolithiasis cases,^[12,13,14,15,16,17,19,21] but earlier studies focussed on the individualized treatment of the cases whereas, in the present study, both constitutional and organopathic medicines were prescribed, which also yielded favourable results. The role of organopathic medicine has also been established in another case report on ureteric calculus.^[23] In the treatment of other chronic diseases like Benign Prostate Hyperplasia^[24,25], the application of constitutional medicines followed by organ specific medicine has been reported which supports the outcomes of our study on urolithiasis.

CONCLUSION

The present case report advocates the potential of Homoeopathy in treating the cases of urolithiasis, where *Calcarea carb.* prescribed as constitutional medicine followed by *Berberis vulgaris φ* as an organopathic remedy, showed positive results. The outcome of this case report will improve the knowledge of the clinicians, which will benefit the patients suffering from urolithiasis, particularly those who want to avoid the risk of surgical interventions. However, a prospective research study with randomised control trial (RCT) study design and a larger sample size is suggested for scientific validation as this was a single case report.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest which have influenced this work.

REFERENCES

1. Moe OW. Kidney stones: Pathophysiology and medical management. *Lancet*. 2006; 367(9507):333-44.
2. Siddiqui VA, Singh H, Gupta J, Nayak C, Singh V, Sinha MN *et al*. A multicentre observational study to ascertain the role of homoeopathic therapy in Urolithiasis. *Indian J Res Homoeopathy*. 2011; 5(2):30-9.
3. Worcester EM, Coe FL. Nephrolithiasis. *Prim Care*. 2008; 35(2):369-91.
4. Asplin JR, Ceo FL, Favus MJ. Nephrolithiasis. In: Braunwald E, Hauser SL, Fauci AS, Kasper DL, Longo DL, Jameson JL *et al*, editors. 17th ed. *Harrison's Principle of Internal Medicine*. New Jersey: McGraw Hill Medical Publishing Division; 2008.
5. Zarse CA, McAteer JA, Sommer AJ, Kim SC, Hatt EK, Lingeman JE *et al*. Non-destructive analysis of urinary calculi using micro computed tomography. *BMC Urology*. 2004; 4:15.
6. Michel MC, de la Rosette JJ. Alpha-blocker treatment of urolithiasis. *Eur Urol*. 2006; 50(2): 213-4.
7. National Health Portal India [homepage on the Internet]. Principles of Prescribing; c2015 [updated 2015 Dec17; cited 2018 June 16]. Available from: https://www.nhp.gov.in/Principles-of-Prescribing_mtl.
8. Monk-Schenk M. Organ Remedies; Our Gift from Paracelsus and Rademacher, with Special Focus on the Liver and Spleen. *The Homeopath*. 2002; 87: 14-19.
9. Blair, J. Organopathy – a relevant approach?. *The Homeopath*. 2009; 28(3): 92-99.
10. Mittelstadt U. A Critical Analysis of Organopathy in Diagnosis and Practice. *Hpathy Ezine* [serial online]. 2010 [cited 2018 June 16]; 7(8). Available from: <https://hpathy.com/homeopathy-papers/a-critical-analysis-of-organopathy-in-diagnosis-and-practice/>
11. Boericke W, Boericke OE. *Pocket Manual of Homoeopathic Materia Medica & Repertory* comprising of the characteristics and guiding symptoms of all remedies. New York: Boericke & Runyon; 1906.
12. Misra A, Nayak C, Paital B. Carcinosis, a boon for paediatric nephrolithiasis: case reports. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*. 2018 ;7(3):922-931.
13. Sharma S, Wadhvani GG. Experience with homoeopathy in a case of large urethral calculus. *Indian J Res Homoeopath*. 2013; 7(4):176-80.
14. Siddiqui VA, Singh H, Gupta J ,Nayak C, SinghV, Dixit R *et al*. A multicentre observational study to ascertain the role of homoeopathic therapy in Urolithiasis. *Indian J Res Homoeopathy*. 2011; 5(2): 30-39.
15. Gupta AK, Gupta J, Siddiqui VA, Mishra A. Case Record: A big urinary calculus expelled with homoeopathic medicine. *Indian J Res Homoeopath*, 2008; 2(4). 50-55.
16. Sumithran PP. A case of multiple urinary calculi. *Indian J Res Homoeopathy*. 2016; 10(2):142-9.
17. Sumithran PP. A case of multiple urinary calculi treated with homoeopathy. *Indian J Res Homoeopathy*. 2011; 5(4): 28-33.
18. Pannek J, Pannek- Rademacher S, Jus MC, Jus MS. Usefulness of classical homoeopathy for the prevention of urinary tract infections in patients with neurogenic bladder dysfunction: A case series. *Indian J Res Homoeopathy*. 2014; 8:31-6.

19. Chakma A. Renal Calculi: An Evidence Based Case Study. RA Journal of Applied Research. 2015; 1(7): 227-234.
20. Gupta G, Singh S. An evidence based case study of benign prostatic hyperplasia. Indian J Res Homoeopathy.2011; 6(3):26-30.
21. Ganesan T, Ravi DB, Vasavan J, Khurana A, Nayak D, Periandavan K. Homoeopathic preparation of Berberis vulgaris as an inhibitor of Calcium oxalate crystallization: An in vitro evidence. Indian J Res Homoeopathy 2015; 9:152-7.
22. Gupta G, Singh S. Role of homoeopathic medicines in prostate enlargement: A retrospective observational study. Indian J Res Homoeopathy 2016; 10:266-71.
23. Nayak Chaturbhujaya, Sahoo Amulya Ratna, Nayak Chintamani, Prusty Umakanta, Hati Akshaya Kumar, Paital Biswaranjan. A Case Report Of Ureteric Calculus Treated with Homoeopathic Medicine Hydrangea Arborescens 30. Indo Am J P. Sci. 2018; 5(1), 627-633.
24. Hati AK, Paital B, Naik KN, Mishra AK, Chainy GB, Nanda LK. Constitutional, organopathic and combined homeopathic treatment of benign prostatic hypertrophy: a clinical trial. Homeopathy. 2012; 101(4):217-23.
25. Paital B, Hati AK, Nayak C, Mishra AK, Nanda LK. Combined Effect of Constitutional and Organopathic Homoeopathic Medicine for better improvement of Benign Prostatic Hyperplasia cases. International Journal of Clinical and Medical Images. 2017; 4(7):1-2.

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